

A case report of a 6-year-old female patient with peripheral ossifying fibroma

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Abstract:- Peripheral ossifying fibroma (POF), when there is damage or irritation to the gingiva, a non-neoplastic growth appears. In 6 year old female patient, a sessile growth was present over maxillary anterior region of size 1*1 cms w.r.t 51,52. Surgical excision of the lesion was done.

Keyword:- Peripheral ossifying Fibroma, surgical excision.

Introduction:-

Peripheral ossifying fibroma (POF), when there is damage or irritation to the gingiva, a non-neoplastic growth appears. Rather than being the soft-tissue counterpart of central ossifying fibroma, it is a connective tissue reactive lesion. Gingival focal fibrous hyperplasia, pyogenic granuloma, peripheral giant cell granuloma, peripheral cementifying fibroma, and peripheral ossifying fibroma are examples of localized reactive lesions ⁽¹⁾.

Shepherd first described POF as alveolar exostosis in 1844 Eversol and Robin gave the term 'peripheral ossifying fibroma' ⁽¹⁾ It mostly affects women and happens in the younger age range. It usually affects the incisor-cuspid region and is more common in the maxillary arch. It appears as a 3 cm long, painless, solitary or pedunculated lump on the alveolar or gingival mucosa. Older lesions have a smooth pink surface and may have surface ulceration

, while earlier lesions are erratic and red ⁽²⁾. Recurrence rates have been found to range from 7 to 45%. The complicated location of POF, which is typically present in interdental locations,

makes it difficult to access during surgical manipulation. These factors could be contributing to the high recurrence incidence, as could insufficient surgical removal of the lesion and incomplete excision of calculus and plaque. ⁽³⁾

CASE REPORT:-

A 6 year old female patient reported to the department of Oral Medicine and Radiology with chief complaint of painless swelling over upper front region since 6 months. fig (1).

Figure (1) A soft tissue overgrowth w.r.t 52

A sessile growth was present over maxillary anterior region of size 1*1 cms in diameter extending antero posteriorly from distal of 51, 52 involving attached gingiva till mesial of 53 and supero inferiorly from 1 cms away from upper labial vestibule involving interdental papillae of 51 and 52 (Fig 2). The shape of the lesion was oval, surface was smooth, colour was pinkish red. Consistency was soft to firm. There was bleeding or any discharge from the lesion. Tenderness was absent. Clinical provisional diagnosis of fibroma was made taking into consideration all the findings and differential diagnosis of peripheral ossifying fibroma, pyogenic granuloma, peripheral giant cell granuloma was given.

Figure (2) A soft tissue overgrowth involving interdental papillae wrt 51, 52

Figure (3) Occlusal radiograph

On radiographic investigation, occlusal radiograph shows soft tissue shadow involving between 51, 52 (fig3).

Fig (4)

Digital Volume Tomography showed a well defined radiolucency of approximately 1*1 cms. Shape was roughly oval, margins were well defined, internal structure shows complete radiolucency. (fig 4).

Fig (5) Flap raised

On excision, under aseptic conditions, local anesthesia was administered. Trapezoidal flap was raised using No. 15 blade. Excision of the lesion was done, irrigation was done at the surgical site, hemostasis was achieved. Suturing was done using interrupted sutures. Post operative instructions were given.(fig 6,7). ZOE pack was applied for better healing. (fig 8)

Fig (6,7) Surgical excision

Fig (8) ZOE pack was applied

Fig (9, 10) 40X - High power view

On histopathologic examination, collagen fiber bundles were distributed in a regular pattern and a t

here was a rich stroma of connective tissue with plump fibroblasts that were proliferating. Normal bone trabeculae bordered with osteoblasts and containing osteocytes are seen in the stroma. Additionally, many well-defined cementum-like elements were observed scattered throughout the stroma in the form of ossicles. There were also many blood arteries with RBCs extravasated in them. The stratified squamous epithelium above was hyperplastic and hyperparakeratinized. (fig 9, 10)

Histological, radiological, and clinical examinations have led to the final diagnosis of peripheral ossifying fibroma.

3. Discussion:-

Since the late 1940s, descriptions of intraoral ossifying fibromas have been documented in literature. Similar lesions have been referred to by several names such as epulis ⁽⁴⁾, peripheral fibroma with calcification ⁽⁴⁾, peripheral ossifying fibroma ^(5,6), calcifying fibroblastic

granuloma⁽⁷⁾, peripheral cementifying fibroma, peripheral fibroma with cementogenesis⁽⁸⁾, peripheral cemento-ossifying fibroma⁽⁹⁾.

It has been proposed that the POF is not a transitional form of irritant fibroma, PGCG, or pyogenic granuloma; rather, it is a distinct clinical entity.⁽⁴⁾ According to Eversole and Rovin⁽⁵⁾, these lesions might just be different histologic reactions to irritation because pyogenic granuloma, PGCG, and POF have similar sex and location predilections as well as comparable clinical and histologic characteristics. According to Gardner⁽⁶⁾, POF cellular connective tissue is so distinctive that, whether calcification is present or not, a histologic diagnosis can be made with certainty. Early POF is thought to manifest as ulcerated nodules with little calcification, which makes it simple to misdiagnose as a pyogenic granuloma, according to Buchner and Hansen's⁽¹⁰⁾ theory.

Making a differential diagnosis is crucial when a gingival lesion is clinically displayed. The differential diagnosis of peripheral ossifying fibroma, pyogenic granuloma, and peripheral giant cell granuloma was made in this case report based on clinical presentation.

It is necessary to distinguish POF from the World Health Organization's description of peripheral odontogenic fibroma (PODF)^{(6),(10)} According to histology, the PODF is an odontogenic epithelium-containing fibroblastic neoplasm⁽¹¹⁾.

As demonstrated in this case, the POF is a soft tissue growth that is confined, reactive, and non-neoplastic. It often originates from the interdental papilla.^{(4),(6)} According to one study, this rather common lesion accounts for about 3% of oral lesions biopsied, whereas other studies report 1%–2%.⁽¹¹⁾⁻⁽¹³⁾

POF might have a wide attachment base or appear as a pedunculated nodule.^{(4),(13),(15)} These lesions can have a smooth or uneven surface, and their color can range from red to pink with patches of ulceration. Although they are usually smaller than 2 cm in diameter^{(10),(15)}, some lesions may be as large as 9 cm. Dimensions may differ, reports range from 0.2–3.0 cm^{(10),(13)}, to 4 mm–8 cm^{(4),(16)}. Although they are uncommon, verified cases of bone degeneration and shifting of teeth do happen⁽¹⁷⁾.

The literature reports a range of female to male ratios, from 1.22:1⁽¹⁸⁾ and 1.7:1⁽¹⁰⁻¹²⁾ to 4.3:1⁽⁵⁾. According to most reports, the incidence of lesions declines with age, with most occurring in the second decade.^(4, 5, 10-12) Two examples of POF that manifest clinically as congenital epuli at birth have been documented^(19, 20) According to a 2001 study by Cuisia and Brannon, only 134 out of 657 confirmed POFs (20%) occurred in the pediatric group (0–19 years old), with 8% occurring in the first decade⁽¹³⁾. In a retrospective investigation of 431 cases in the Chinese population, Zhang and colleagues (2016) found that the mean age of POF incidence was 44 years. This finding contradicts other research that has been published in the review. POF appears to be considerably less common among people of Hispanic heritage⁽¹⁴⁾ and more common among albinos than blacks⁽¹³⁾.

Depending on the extent of ulceration, irritation, and functional hindrance, the lesion may exist for several months to years prior surgical removal^(4,10) POFs are more prevalent in the anterior than the posterior region^(11,14,18), with the incisor-cuspid region accounting for 55% to 60%^(4, 5, 10, 13, 18) of instances. Approximately 60% of POFs occur in the maxilla^(10,11,18).

POFs are thought to arise as hyperplastic tissue proliferation specific to the gingival mucosa from the gingival fibers of the periodontal ligament^(4-6,21) Theory was supported by the observation that periodontal ligament-associated missing teeth are inversely correlated with the age distribution of the patients who came in with periodontal failures (POFs), the fact that gingiva is the only tissue on which POFs arise, and the gingiva's subsequent proximity to the periodontal ligament.^(11,13) Just two of the 134 young patients in the study had POF that was closely linked to their main teeth, raising concerns about the lesion's responsiveness. Reactive lesions associated with the periodontal ligament should be more common as a consequence of primary teeth exfoliating and their successors erupting.^(5,13) Given that POF is more prevalent in women, spikes throughout the second decade, and falls after the third, it is possible that hormonal considerations play vital a role⁽¹¹⁾.

Histology indicates that the POF is a nonencapsulated mass of cellular fibroblastic connective tissue produced from mesenchymal tissue.⁽⁶⁾, coated in stratified squamous epithelium that is ulcerated in 23%–66% of cases.^(4,10) Patients experience the majority of ulcerated lesions in their second decade.^(5,10) POFs have regions of mineralization, endothelial proliferation, and fibrous connective tissue.

In ulcerated areas, endothelial growth might be abundant. This can be deceiving in terms of clinical diagnosis, as the lesion might seem like a PG.⁽⁴⁾ The percentage of POF that is mineralized varies; it can be found in roughly 23%, 35%, or 50%–75%.^(4,23,10) of cases based on reports that have been released. There are three types of mineralization: dystrophic calcification, braided and lamellar bone, and cementum-like substance.^(4,23,10) Since the POF lesion is typically tiny, radiographs are the only imaging needed.^(6,24)

Scaling of neighboring teeth and conservative surgical excision^(4,11) make up the course of treatment.⁽⁶⁾

Recurrence rates of 8.9%, 1 9%, 11 14%, 9 16%8, and 20% have all been documented.⁽⁵⁾ As a result, frequent follow-up is necessary.

Conclusion:-

POF is a slowly developing lesion with typically restricted growth. Due to the absence of symptoms related to the lesion, many cases will continue to progress for extended periods of time before patients seek therapy. A POF should be suspected if a teenager has a pink soft tissue nodule in their anterior maxilla that is slowly expanding.

In current case, the lesion involves the inter dental dental papillae of 51, 52. It is pinkish red in colour, firm in consistency. Histopathological and radiographical reports suggests

peripheral ossifying fibroma. Excision via surgery is the method of treatment. Thorough postoperative monitoring is necessary.

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